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University-Industry Collaboration in Sri Lanka – A Developing Country Perspective

ABSTRACT

Many advanced economies are at the forefront of the growth of university-industry collaborations. But many developing countries have yet to fully implement this type of important linkage phenomenon. We report empirical findings from our study conducted in Sri Lanka to provide more explanations on the nature of U-I collaboration in developing countries. We used multiple methods to collect empirical data, namely a questionnaire survey, interviews with university academic staff and a few company managers, held focus group workshops and exploited secondary data on national government sponsorship initiatives linked to U-I collaboration. This paper discusses key practical implications around current modes of U-I collaboration, barriers to collaboration and funding of collaboration, which provide a number of valuable lessons for the advancement of knowledge.

KEYWORDS

Universities; industry; collaboration; Sri Lanka; qualitative research; quantitative research; focus groups.

INTRODUCTION

Universities are a platform for the development of a country. In developing countries, universities are playing a prominent role in national innovation systems (NIS), and some have managed to learn how to interact with other actors (Fortin, Marceau, & Savard, 1997). In any NIS, successful university-industry (U-I) collaboration brings numerous benefits to universities, industrial firms, and to the socio-economic development of the country (Khorsheed & Al-Fawzan, 2014). Still, the objectives and expectations of universities and

industrial firms have considerable differences (Barnes, Pashby, & Gibbons, 2002). The main aim of universities is to produce public knowledge for society. To achieve this objective, a university sets its own academic priorities such as undergraduate employability, qualifications for postgraduate students and publication of research outcomes. In contrast, firms aim to maximize competitive advantage by pursuing private knowledge generation. To achieve this objective, a firm sets its own priorities, such as a short-term focus on research projects. These divergent goals often cause problems in U-I collaboration and raise questions on the benefits realized by each party.

This paper attempts to provide an understanding on the role of universities, and academics' perceptions and experiences of U-I collaboration in a developing country – Sri Lanka. Universities in developing countries face comparatively higher levels of resource scarcity in terms of capabilities, finance, and physical infrastructure. Hence, it is vital to explore when academics operate in a resource constrained environment, how does this influence their ability to collaborate with industrial firms? Considering these factors, we aim to address the following research questions in this paper:

- 1) What is the present context and level of U-I collaboration prevailing within Sri Lankan universities? and
- 2) How do universities and academics operate in a resource constrained environment like Sri Lanka?

The paper is organized as follows. The next section presents a literature review on the main theme of the paper, which includes some insights into the Sri Lankan country context, where our empirical study was conducted. Thereafter, the research methodology is presented, followed by an analysis of our empirical research findings, before presenting conclusions and discussing implications in the final section.

LITERATURE REVIEW

With the rise of knowledge-based economies, the importance of U-I collaboration increased, and universities as well as firms have attempted to develop close relationships with the intention of mutual benefits. Metcalfe (2010, p. 7) states “two worlds of universities and businesses form coupled subsystems of a complex adaptive system, which are continuously forming new system components, new connections and shifting boundaries”. Universities

have undergone profound changes in their policies and interactions with industry, for example, universities are seeking financial support from industry for research (Drabenstott, 2008; Feritas, 2008; Grimaldi et al., 2011; Huggins, 2008). However, little is known about complex and constantly evolving U-I collaboration in developing countries, especially what is the role played by universities in developing countries?

In the fields of innovation systems, research policy, and higher education research, the Triple Helix model has been commonly used as a normative framework for understanding interactions between key actors in innovation systems. The Triple Helix model is seen as a spiral model that captures the reciprocal relationship between public, private and academic spheres in capitalization of knowledge (Etzkowitz & Leydesdorff, 2000). This model highlights interaction among the three helices (university, company and government), which should help to generate new organizational innovations (Dzisah and Etzkowitz, 2008). Each helix has an internal core and external field space, where the external field space provides the overlaps between the three key actors. The path of the Triple Helix development begins from two opposing starting points (Etzkowitz, 2003). One is the *statist model*, where government is the dominant institutional sphere, while industry and academia are subordinate parts of the state. The other starting point is the *laissez-faire model*, where industry, academia, and government are separate, interacting only modestly across strong boundaries. Here, the connection between university and industry is restricted to university providing knowledge and trained persons. Although it is difficult to fully implement a triple helix model in developing countries, mainly due to many other policy priorities to improve economic and social conditions in a country, there is some scope to partly implement this model. For example, where high rates of unemployment exist, the need to increase employability and entrepreneurial behavior becomes an important priority when confronting such challenges (Plewa et al, 2015). In the face of this type of challenge, a country may decide to prioritize some elements of a triple helix model by improving university student skills and knowledge through greater contact and cooperation with business during their studies to help the students become more employable (Gibb & Hannon, 2006).

Freitas (2008) identifies the main determinants of U-I collaboration as the role of universities in NIS (actors), configuration of NIS itself (networks) and nature of activities of firms. Segarra-Blasco and Arauzo-Carod (2008) showed that a firm's cooperation activities in developing countries are closely linked to the characteristics of industries and firms. In developing countries, U-I collaboration could not be measured merely based on academic

papers published in mainstream publications, as academics may have few connections, and universities may have a higher level of teaching priority to address the needs of a country's capability building. Therefore, U-I environment that exists in developing countries may be different to what is prevailing in developed countries. Studies by Grimpe and Fier (2010) and Khorsheed and Al-Fawzan (2014) have showed the need to better understand and evaluate U-I collaboration and institutional conditions in developing countries, in order to provide meaningful information to make comparisons with developed countries.

There is limited evidence of recent literature that compares the trajectory of U-I collaborations across South Asian countries. There are a few individual country accounts of this phenomenon [e.g. Homma, Ikeda and Attalage (2008): covered in next section]. Schiller and Lee (2015) present a comparative analysis of U-I links in five Asian countries (China, India, Korea, Malaysia and Thailand) where they stress the need to build trust-based relations to promote U-I collaborations. This is due to a lack of trust between science and industry in these Asian countries, partly because of lack of interaction in the past. Also the UNESCO Science report (2015) sheds some light on common challenges that might be inhibiting U-I collaborations in South Asia. For example, public-private partnerships can be an important component in promoting U-I linkages, as long as the private sector is sufficiently robust to shoulder some of the burden. This report adds that public-private partnerships can help to create synergies between firms and universities to assist with more industry-led innovations (especially in South Asian economies like Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Nepal, Pakistan and Sri Lanka). Some other insights that highlight U-I collaborations in resource constrained environments may provide useful lessons for government, universities and industry in Sri Lanka and other developing economies. For example, Pakistan's *National Science, Technology and Innovation Policy 2012* (Government of Pakistan, 2012) initiated the establishment of a new national materials science research institute with a centralized supercomputing facility that had the remit of acting as an interface between universities and industry. This gives scope for some U-I interaction at a national research centre, which has been identified as an important area for various stakeholders in the country. From Thailand's Hard Disk Drive (HDD) industry, we learn that intermediaries have played a prominent brokering and mediating role that has enabled some U-I collaboration for this industry sector. Some of these intermediaries are public funded and they have provided resources (e.g. information, training and testing) to university and industry to help deepen and strengthen the U-I relationships (Sutthijakra and Intarakumnerd, 2015).

Perkmann et al. (2013) present a comprehensive review of recent literature on university-industry relations, mainly in relation to the economies of Europe and USA. However, some of these insights might have relevance for Sri Lanka and other developing countries in Asia. For example, Perkman et al. (2013) attach importance to the role of key productive individuals in establishing and maintaining U-I collaborations. They confirm that academic engagement is often pursued by scientists who are well established and well connected in the academic community. Individuals who are more senior, have more social capital, more publications and more government grants, also work most prolifically with industrial collaborators. Previous experience with industrial collaborators can positively affect the attitudes of academics towards industry.

Sri Lankan context

As confirmed by Perkmann et al. (2013), most U-I collaboration studies focus on the United States and selected European countries while contributions covering other geographical regions are rare. Hence we aim to address this gap by providing some insights from Sri Lanka. Lying off the southern tip of India, the tropical island of Sri Lanka has a population of approximately 22 million people. After more than 25 years of civil conflict, which ended in May 2009, the country can now look forward to improved economic and social prosperity. Sri Lanka is a developing economy largely based on agriculture, services, and light industry. The service sector is the largest sector of the Sri Lankan economy, employing 44% of the workforce. Tourism, banking, finance, and retail trade are the major components of the service sector (U.S. Department of State, 2015). Some useful industry data is presented in Appendix 1 to 3. As illustrated in Appendix 1: the highest industrial production from Sri Lanka is in the category of ‘food, beverages and tobacco products’ (47% as a percentage of total population); followed by the categories of ‘textiles, wearing apparel and leather products’ (23% as a percentage of total population); and ‘chemical, petroleum, coal, rubber and plastics products’ (16% as a percentage of total population). Appendix 2 shows that the vast majority (94.4%) of Sri Lankan establishments employ 5 or less persons. Appendix 3 shows Sri Lanka’s ‘human development index’ in comparison to ten other Asian economies, as well as providing data on the country’s percentage ‘share of output’ and ‘share of employment’ within the following categories: agriculture, industry, services, high-tech and non high-tech sectors.

There are 15 conventional state universities in Sri Lanka. With regard to research in the universities, 67 PhDs (1%), 129 MPhils (2%), 5518 other postgraduate degrees (97%) were awarded in 2013. Of the PhDs, 50% (33 of 67) were in pure sciences. In terms of research volume and reputation (based on publications from 2008 to 2012), top contributing Sri Lankan institutions were University of Peradeniya, University of Colombo, University of Moratuwa, University of Ruhuna, University of Sri Jayawardenapura, University of Kelaniya and The Open University of Sri Lanka. Non-university institutions were Ministry of Health, International Water Management Institute, National Hospital of Sri Lanka, Industrial Technology Institute, Teaching Hospital of Kandy and Institute of Fundamental Studies (Fernando, 2015). Still, Sri Lanka is rated in the 105th position (out of 143 countries) in both innovation index and knowledge economy index rankings in 2012 (Ministry of Technology and Research, 2014). As a country, Sri Lanka is in a very low position in obtaining intellectual patent rights compared to other countries in the Asian region (Ministry of Technology and Research, 2014). According to Ministry of Technology and Research (2014), research output of Sri Lankan scientists in terms of publications in journals covered by the Science Citation Index (SCI) just exceeds 300; almost similar number of papers is published in SCI “expanded” journals; a large number of papers are also published in other recognized refereed journals. With the backing of the University Grants Commission (UGC) of Sri Lanka, universities through different award schemes popularize research output in international research outlets (UGC, non-dated). It is possible to interpret this situation as governments of Sri Lanka having limited focus on Triple Helix model, but prefer other models such as “academics publishing in international journals”.

In Sri Lanka, although governments formally started supporting U-I collaboration since 2005, this activity area has received limited leadership, direction or monitoring from within the university sector. We identified the following from secondary information sources as the three main government led mechanisms promoting U-I collaboration in the chronological order of implementation:

1. The Sri Lankan government formally started to support U-I collaboration from 2005, when UGC issued the circular granting one year leave for senior university academics to work in any industrial establishment (UGC, non-dated).
2. In 2014, the government of Sri Lanka introduced a mechanism of triple tax deduction from the industry if they collaborate with universities in doing research (Mendes, 2015, p. 23). As a result, universities such as University of Colombo, University of

Kelaniya, and The Open University of Sri Lanka established formal units dedicated for U-I collaboration.

3. The latest initiative introduced by UGC in 2015 provides some funding that could include an element of U-I collaboration within the following areas: (1) research and innovation in universities – pure sciences; (2) research that directly impact on communities; (3) post-doctoral research for academic staff just completed their PhDs; (4) local and international training for university academics; and (5) soft loans for academics to commercialize products developed through R&D (UGC, non-dated).

However, according to Weerasinghe and Jayawardane (2015) Sri Lankan academics mainly conduct research for their own interest. Collaborative industry based research activities are rare across universities in Sri Lanka. Weerasinghe and Jayawardane (2015) identify the main mode of U-I collaboration in Sri Lanka as student internship programmes, from which both university and industry reap mutual benefits.

De Silva (2012) infers that it has been difficult to promote U-I collaboration in Sri Lanka, partly due to the absence of an overall university policy or support mechanisms to promote academic entrepreneurship. Any such small scale initiatives are mainly driven by individual academics. Homma et al. (2008) provide some evidence for resources received from the International Cooperation Center for Engineering Education Development (ICCEED) of Toyohashi University of Technology (TUT), Japan for introducing methods and experience of U-I collaboration in Japan to strengthen university-industry collaboration in developing countries, with special reference to University of Moratuwa, Sri Lanka. The objectives of this project at the Faculty of Engineering, University of Moratuwa were (1) capacity building of U-I collaboration coordinators, (2) development of a monitoring and evaluation mechanism of U-I collaboration including intellectual property aspects, and (3) development of a sustainable mechanism of generation and management of a research fund.

According to Homma et al. (2008), the Engineering Faculties of leading universities in Sri Lanka employ several mechanisms for enhancing U-I linkage. Some of the most common mechanisms were conducting undergraduate projects with some industry component, undertaking consultancy tasks by the faculty members at the request of industry, and conducting other outreach activities such as seminars, workshops, testing etc. for industry. Homma et al. (2008) further identify the UNI-Consultancy Service, which is the commercial arm of the University of Moratuwa registered under the company ordinance of

Sri Lanka and the Center for Engineering Research and Postgraduate Studies (CERPS) at the University of Peradeniya as other mechanisms of promoting U-I linkages in Engineering Faculties in Sri Lanka. In addition, Homma et al. (2008) reveal that the individual departments of the Engineering Faculties as having their Department Industry Consultative Boards (DICB) and the faculties as a whole having Faculty Industry Consultative Boards (FICB) to interact with the industry with reference to policy and curricula development matters. However, the output of these mechanisms are still far from expected levels due to many challenges and issues faced by the engineering education system of the country.

Some of the above developments also coincide with Esham's (2008) findings, who stated that it may be appropriate to consider the setting-up of a higher level body to provide direction to industry interaction cells setup at universities. This higher body should comprise representatives from both university and industry in advisory capacities and should recruit personnel with strong leadership qualities and experience in industry and university affairs to provide the much needed guidance to the cells at universities. As far as industry is concerned, given the scale and diversity of local industries it is highly unlikely for each firm to come up with a liaison office of its own to interact with universities. Hence, Esham (2008) recommended that the more feasible approach would be to setup liaison offices with the involvement of an industry association such as the chambers of commerce and industry.

METHODOLOGY

To find answers to our main research questions, we conducted an empirical study to explore the status of U-I collaboration in Sri Lanka. Here we report on findings related to two main objectives (and sub objectives) we derived in line with our research questions, when exploring evidence of U-I collaboration, especially from the universities' perspective:

1) To investigate the present context and level of U-I collaboration prevailing in Sri Lanka universities:

- 1.1) To investigate the level of U-I collaboration prevailing in the universities.
- 1.2) To identify the mode of collaboration with industry.
- 1.3) To identify barriers in preventing collaboration with industry.
- 1.4) To investigate major problems related to maintaining existing relationships with industrial firms.
- 1.5) To investigate factors that can help to build successful relationships with industrial firms.

2) To investigate whether universities and academics operate in a resource constrained environment:

2.1) To investigate sources of funding that universities might access for undertaking some form of R&D and innovation activities.

2.2) To investigate the importance of U-I collaboration for academic career advancement.

2.3) To investigate academics' motivations for U-I collaboration.

Research design

The study used multiple methods to collect empirical data from Sri Lanka. Of these, the main method of data collection was a questionnaire survey targeted at academics in Sri Lankan universities. In addition, we conducted some interviews to obtain more depth insights of the scenario at hand. These interviews were conducted with university academic staff and a few company managers. We obtained some secondary data on national government sponsorship initiatives linked to U-I collaboration. We also held one focus group workshop with employees from different industry sectors (in Colombo, June 2015) and another workshop with representatives from universities and some national research institutes (in Colombo, December 2015). This paper analyses empirical data collected from all the above mentioned sources to investigate current U-I collaboration phenomena in Sri Lanka.

Survey – sample, measures and methods of data analysis

The main method of data collection was the survey questionnaire administered to university academics. Eight Sri Lankan state universities were selected for our questionnaire survey. These eight universities were selected after our preliminary investigations that led to exclude seven universities due their lack of involvement in U-I collaboration. Of the eight universities, four were established during the period of 1940 to 1960, three were established during the period of 1970 to 1980, and one was established after 1999. These eight universities included the country's top contributing universities in terms of research volume and reputation. Since all these universities are public sector institutions, their regulatory and cost structure remained same (or similar/no difference). We covered the Faculties of Applied Sciences, Medicine, Engineering, Computer Science, and Information Technology (IT) in conducting interviews and the survey. For our

questionnaire survey, the key senior academics (professor and senior lecturer grades) involved in U-I collaboration responded. We identified an academic as a contact person from each university. The first author of this paper together with the contact persons isolated the respondents from their role in research and publications in each university. A total of 65 key senior academics involved in U-I collaboration across eight universities identified as respondents, where larger number of respondents came from larger universities in terms of research activities. The aims of the survey were explained and the respondents were given the choice of responding anonymously. We received 43 fully completed questionnaire responses through contact persons, yielding a 66% response rate.

We designed the measures based on the insights gained from the literature reviewed above, such as De Silva (2012), Esham (2008), Homma et al. (2008), Perkmann et al. (2013), and Schiller and Lee (2015). For example, De Silva (2012) presents a questionnaire survey that gathers evidence of any academic entrepreneurial activities in Sri Lankan universities. Schiller and Lee (2015) provide some insights from recent surveys conducted in South Korea and Thailand. Hence these types of literature sources were a useful guide for the design of our survey questionnaire. We used diverse measurement scales ranging from yes/no, multiple choice to Likert-scale. Almost all Likert-scale questions used a five-point scale, except the scale used to identify barriers preventing U-I collaboration with industry, which we converted into a three-point scale after the pilot test. All question items were first, assessed by a panel of academics and practitioners, and second, pre-tested with a sample of targeted academics. All the survey responses were tabulated and analyzed through descriptive statistics. Factor analysis (principle component with Varimax rotation) as a method of data reduction was performed on the three questions on Likert-scale responses, i.e., mechanisms for establishing U-I collaboration, barriers in preventing U-I collaboration with industry, and factors motivating academics for U-I collaboration.

Interviews – sample, measures and methods of data analysis

Interviews were deemed necessary to complement the survey questionnaire to corroborate the information that had been gathered from the survey questionnaires and to elaborate the field by exploring a greater variety of experiences offered by academics and a few company managers. We conducted 12 interviews with academics involved in U-I collaboration from some of the Sri Lankan universities that had responded to our questionnaire survey. The aim of conducting interviews was to confirm the information obtained from the

questionnaire survey. It is anticipated that the results of the survey questionnaire may provide access to breadth of experience while the interviews may provide depth by adding insight and substance to the questionnaire survey. It was decided to conduct interviews after the preliminary analysis of data obtained from the self-administered questionnaire for two reasons. First, the answers to the survey questionnaire may provide the researcher some new insights, which should be further investigated. Second, if the researcher discovered something that should have been asked but was omitted in the questionnaires, then those areas can be dealt with during the interviews.

We obtained the assistance of academic staff involved in U-I activities to identify company managers, from companies that support U-I collaboration in universities. We conducted interviews with 8 company managers. Since survey was conducted with academics, we expected to obtain industry perspective in line with survey objectives. In the section on results we present interview data with academics and company managers separately.

A pre-prepared interview guide was used for the interviews. The responses were recorded appropriately. Interview responses were analysed through critical reviewing and content analysis to provide a credible picture of the situation at hand.

Focus group – sample, measures and methods of data analysis

We conducted two workshops on U-I collaboration in Colombo, Sri Lanka. The first workshop was held in June 2015 with approximately 40 employees from different industry sectors. All participants had Bachelor's degrees from the areas of Applied Sciences, Medicine, Engineering, Computer Science, and Information Technology (IT) to match with our university survey sample. Participants were identified from research and taught Masters degree programmes conducted by a few universities. All participants had industry experience over three years and had some sort of knowledge and experience on U-I collaborations.

The second workshop was held in December 2015 with a similar number of participants, but fewer industry side people. The industry representatives were identified from leading organizations that support U-I collaboration. When selecting academics, a few were randomly selected from our survey sample. In addition to these academics, we had invited a considerable number of academics who are knowledgeable of U-I collaboration and may have participated in U-I activities in their universities to some level.

Pre-prepared guides were used for both workshops. The responses were recorded appropriately. Responses were analysed through critical reviewing and content analysis to provide a credible picture of the situation at hand.

RESULTS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE SURVEY

We first present results to elaborate the present context of U-I collaboration prevailing in Sri Lanka - our first objective. Second, we present results relating to academics' reactions to U-I collaboration in a resource constrained environment in Sri Lanka - our second objective.

The present context and level of U-I collaboration

We collected data to describe present context of U-I collaboration prevailing in Sri Lanka in terms of five areas, namely, 1) level of U-I collaboration, 2) mode of U-I collaboration, 3) barriers in preventing collaboration with industry, 4) problems in maintaining existing relationships with industrial firms, and 5) factors related to successful relationships with industrial firms. Results relating to these five aspects are presented below.

Level of U-I collaboration

Forty two per cent of the respondents identified their respective universities' collaboration with the industry as "much better" while 52% identified this activity as "good". 89% of respondents identified their universities' owning some form of patents, licenses or copyrights for their R&D activities. We inquired whether academics perceive U-I collaboration as a part of state universities mandate. 90% of the respondents identified U-I collaboration as a "very important" part of their university's mandate while remaining 10% identified U-I collaboration as an "important" part of their university's mandate. 67% identified that university has a formal policy on allowing academic staff outside activities such as consultancy to industry while 33% identified as not having such a formal policy. Also 35% of the respondents confirmed that their university has an industrial liaison office (or technology transfer unit) while 65% stated their university does not have such an office. Furthermore, 97% stated that they have observed that their university's collaboration with industry has increased in the last 5 years while only 3% stated their university's collaboration with industry remained the same in the last 5 years. Finally, 71% of the respondents stated their university will further strengthen (considerable improvements can be seen) its interactions

with industry within next year while 29 % expected to see such improvements within the next 3 years.

Mode of U-I collaboration

As shown in Table 1, the majority of U-I collaboration followed by Sri Lankan universities appear to be through “student placements in industry” and “consultancy to industry by academic staff”. The next most important modes of collaboration were seen as “research contracted to university staff” and “training of industry staff at university”.

Table 1

With regard to student placement in industry, to date almost all undergraduates (from the university Faculties that we surveyed) spend a 6 to 12 month compulsory industrial training period as part of their respective degree programme.

With regard to training of industry staff at university, 96% of the respondents stated that training courses offered by the university meet the expectations of industry. Furthermore, 84 % of the respondents identified as receiving some sort of (formal or informal) feedback from industry about the courses offered by the university. 90% observe encouragement from the universities to involve students to conduct their research projects in industry or in collaboration with industry.

In terms of the most important mechanisms used for establishing collaborative links with industry, as shown in Table 2, the most highly ranked mechanisms used are as follows: (1) “access to specialized technical reports, equipment and industrial R&D”; (2) “participation in research contract and joint research”; (3) “invention originating in university taken up by existing industrial companies”; (4) “analysis and testing in industry”; and (5) “consultancy to industry by academics”.

Table 2

Results of factor analysis for mechanisms used for establishing collaborations are presented in Table 3. The 9-item measure had total item Cronbach’s alpha of 0.85. As shown in

Table 3, factor analysis yielded three factors. The total variance explained by the three factors was 74.36.

Table 3

Barriers in preventing U-I collaboration with industry

Barriers to establishing collaborative links with industry were ranked in Table 4 somewhat differently from those for mechanisms shown in Table 2, perhaps reflecting the lack of incentives for academics to pursue this line of activity, as shown in Table 5. To calculate the means shown, a score of three was given to a “very significant” barrier, two was given for a “moderately significant” barrier, and one was given for a “not significant” barrier. Hence the major barriers are identified as: (1) “insufficient experience in New Product Development (NPD) and commercialization”; (2) “cannot respond to needs of industry because our equipment base and facilities are insufficient”; (3) “poor knowledge of industry relevant needs”; (4) “differences in objectives of the university and company”; and (5) “work required by industry not always interesting for us”. Other barriers ranked lower than these five refer to institutional working arrangements of university staff perhaps not being conducive to taking on external collaborative tasks such as the ones listed in barriers 9 to 12 in Table 4.

Table 4

Results of factor analysis for barriers to establish collaborative links with industry are presented in Table 5. The 12-item measure had total item Cronbach’s alpha of 0.901. As shown in Table 5, factor analysis yielded three factors. The total variance explained by the three factors was 72.44.

Table 5

Problems related to maintaining existing relationships with industrial firms

For those universities that have some experience of collaborating with industry, Table 6 highlights some of the main challenges (or problems) faced in maintaining relationships with industrial firms.

Table 6

Important factors related to successful relationships with industrial firms

As shown in Table 7 below, we asked about the most important factors related to successful relationships with industrial firms.

Table 7

The nature of the academic environment

We collected data to describe the nature of the academic environment prevailing in Sri Lanka in terms of three areas, namely, 1) sources of funding academics have access for R&D activities, 2) importance of U-I collaboration for academic career advancement, and 3) academics' motivations for U-I collaboration. Using these three criteria, we aimed to understand academics' reactions to U-I collaboration in a resource constrained environment in Sri Lanka. Results relating to these three areas are presented below.

Sources of funding academics have access for R&D activities

We questioned the sources of funding for academics to collaborate with industry. As illustrated in Table 8, our results show that national public funded schemes are seen as an important policy instrument to help trigger U-I collaboration in a developing country like Sri Lanka.

Table 8

With regard to overseas funding, Alumni and former colleagues living abroad, contacts with academics who completed PhDs in the developed countries, and international partnership programs are identified as the sources of funding from overseas.

We also explored to what extent universities participate in government funded schemes for working with industry. Table 9 shows results relating to participation of universities in any government funded scheme/project for working with industry.

Table 9

To further understand the situation in Sri Lanka, we explored the factors that influenced the academics to establish U-I collaboration with industry. Table 10 illustrates important factors that influenced academics to seek out collaborative opportunities with industry partners.

Table 10

Importance of U-I collaboration for academic career advancement

With regard to perceived importance of U-I collaboration for academic career advancement, 77% of the respondents identified U-I collaboration as a “very important” part of their academic career advancement, 16% identified it as “important” for their academic career advancement, while the remaining 7% identified U-I collaboration as “not important” for their academic career advancement. 55% of the respondents stated that it is fair to evaluate academic members according to the extent of their contributions to the U-I collaboration processes while remaining 45% did not agree.

Academics’ motivations for U-I collaboration

In terms of factors that motivate academics to consider establishing collaborative links with industry, as shown in Table 11, the university academics rated (1) “to access industrial feedback for graduates and curriculum development” as the main motivating factor. The next most important factor was that collaboration with industry was seen as

giving universities (2) “access to complementary expertise in industry”. Another significant factor was that collaboration with industry provided an opportunity (3) “to train students in an industrial environment”. The next most important motivations were (4) “to make a contribution to country’s economy”, and (5) “to find an exploitation outlet for research capabilities”.

Table 11

Results of factor analysis for academic motivations are presented in Table 12. The 9-item measure had total item Cronbach’s alpha of 0.732. As shown in Table 12, factor analysis yielded three factors. The total variance explained by the three factors was 67.16.

Table 12

RESULTS FROM INTERVIEWS

Interviews with academics

Interviews with academics involved in U-I collaboration helped to confirm the following key points.

First, at the very basic level all the universities irrespective of the Faculty (e.g., Engineering, Medical, Applied Science, Management, Agriculture, Humanities) do provide industry oriented training programs. Some are courses leading to a qualification, postgraduate diploma, MSc, MBA, etc. In addition, they provide customized training programs to suit specific industry needs upon request. Further, some universities offer programs on an e-learning platform.

Second, all universities to some extent are involved in providing different types of dedicated services to the government agencies and the private sector, as consultancy services. For instance, Faculty of Medicine providing the Ministry of Health and many private sector firms with services such as biochemical, pharmacological, hematological, genetic, microbiological, pathological, parasitological, obstetric and gynecological. Additionally,

Agriculture Faculties are providing services to the government agencies and the private sector, by performing multi-disciplinary R&D in plants and animals involving agricultural, medical, dental, aqua-culture, livestock, forestry, environment, indigenous medicine, and pharmaceuticals.

Third, at a higher level of interactions, we identified one university that hosts some industry sponsored laboratories. The government agencies and the private sector often approach these laboratories for consultancy services, demonstrating another type of U-I collaboration. Fourth, two universities, two government agencies and a Japanese university were involved in an internationally funded project on pollution control and remediation techniques for waste landfill sites in Sri Lanka.

Interviews with industry participants

We conducted a few interviews with some industry representatives. One official from a chemical manufacturing firm identified that charges for the services are reasonable and services are identified as accurate and reliable when the services are obtained from universities. An officer from an international non-government organization (NGO) stated that they approach universities to get assistance in environmental assessment activities. Another officer from a government health related organization confirmed that Medical Faculties support government health initiatives. This officer also acknowledged that they have good relations with Humanities Faculties too, and gave evidence for taking assistance from a Humanities Faculty to conduct a broad based survey on health issues pertaining to internal migration covering a substantial portion of the country.

However, industry representatives are unanimous in identifying the following as problems (or barriers) to maintaining collaborative relationships with universities: bureaucratic system prevailing in the universities; lack of experienced staff to deal with industry; university and industry objectives are different and considerable efforts are needed to match these objectives; universities are more concerned about their teaching rather than maintaining relations with industry; there is insufficient business know-how with universities. Some of the industry representatives also mentioned the following as more generic type of challenges to U-I collaboration in Sri Lanka: lack of support for industrial research from universities or government; most industrial firms are reluctant to spend money on research; change of attitudes of all parties is very important; there should be a mechanism to link universities with small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs).

RESULTS FROM FOCUS GROUP WORKSHOPS

Some of the key issues arising from our two workshops held in Colombo are highlighted here. One of the key issues arising was that U-I research partnerships, such as the types of collaboration described above, enables companies to integrate corporate R&D resources with university resources as part of a long-term partnership. This allows university research staff to benefit from insights into future business areas that firms are working in, while the sponsoring company gains access to the wider expertise available in the university community. The workshops highlighted a number of existing barriers and challenges that might inhibit U-I collaboration in Sri Lanka. The participants also provided some suggestions of how to address and overcome some of these challenges.

One issue mentioned by most participants is that there firstly needs to be a culture developed within universities, which recognises the value of business and commercial engagement, by creating awareness among academics about the importance of commercialising their research results. Universities could properly utilize the contact with industry employees, who might be their ex-students, to identify needs of future continuing professional developments. At the same time, firms from the private sector, as well as trade associations need to be made aware of the variety of linkages that can be created directly and indirectly with higher education institutions. Hence, there appears to be a lack of understanding about what each of the partners can bring to such collaborations. This is partly linked to the fact that outputs of firms are seen to be more practical based and outputs from universities are less practical and perhaps more theoretical based. Hence, there needs to be some mechanism to help improve the understanding of what the universities and firms can offer to each other.

One suggestion made is to create a national institute that acts as an industry-academia coordination body that can highlight the benefits of U-I collaboration to both universities and firms and it can set-up some forums that bring together these key actors at seminar and conference type events to gain a better understanding of the needs of potential collaborators. Here, it was also mentioned that the government can play an important role by helping to set-up such a national coordination body. Furthermore, universities could be more proactive in providing some form of knowledge transfer sessions to company staff on latest technological developments that some university research groups are working on. In return, the industry participants may be able to suggest some potential applications for taking the research results

from universities into industry and potential commercialization. These types of forums might be organised around key themes that are of interest to the universities and industry, which could include environmental science, telecommunications, IT, sustainability, agricultural sciences, textile technology and a range of other areas. Postgraduate and undergraduate students could also act as facilitators of collaboration and other forms of knowledge transfer between universities and the private sector. For example, it was mentioned that some universities already offer some of their students' opportunities to implement some of their research projects with industry partners, so this could be expanded in the future. Where feasible, some university departments may consider working closely with industry for assistance with curriculum development whereby students are developing the type of skills that will help them to secure graduate jobs after completing their undergraduate studies as industrial firms would be able to benefit from hiring students with both academic and practical related skills.

DISCUSSION

Models of collaboration

When gaining insight from Triple Helix, the findings suggest that Sri Lankan U-I collaborations seem to be more aligned with a statist society (Etzkowitz, 2003), where government is the dominant institutional sphere that controls, on the one hand, the activities of the universities through financing and regulating activities through UGC, and promoting some U-I collaboration via special funding programs. On the other hand, government controls the activities of firms through its financial regulations (i.e., tax reductions). In short, the Government of Sri Lanka implements science, technology and innovation policies; promotes synergies with industry through tax reduction programs; implements education policies at all levels; and finances the university system of the country.

As indicated by the empirical research results, most Sri Lankan industrial firms are reluctant to spend money on research and most universities are hampered by lack of finance to promote collaborative R&D with industry. Hence one option for the Government of Sri Lanka might be to promote university-industry R&D cooperation via subsidies to help overcome the finance constraint that hinders such collaborations. For example, grants could be provided by Government to share the financial risk of an R&D project with the aim of stimulating innovation and wealth creation. Industrial firms of any size and local universities should be able to access funding with relative ease avoiding any administrative hurdles to

obtain the funding. Here the Government might decide to provide 50% or more contribution to the R&D project cost (dependent on the nature of the project as it could be a feasibility study or near to market development project). The remaining proportion of funding should come from the private sector firms. Therefore the firms are incentivized to undertake a collaborative R&D project with a university, with a reduced funding commitment as the firm takes advantage of the Government subsidy.

Funding from U-I collaboration

Findings suggest that Sri Lankan universities aim to obtain industrial funding from U-I collaboration (Table 9). This supports Homma et al.'s (2008) point that university linking up with industry will lead to increased funding to universities in Sri Lanka. We collected data from Faculties of Applied Sciences, Medicine, Engineering, Computer Science, and IT, where much of the applied research is carried out. The funding for industry adds much value in enhancing applied research and gaining technical competence, especially in the developing world. This supports Gunasekara (2006) who state funding to be significantly related to applied research and Homma et al. (2008) who state funding is much needed for developing countries with low technical competence and capabilities. Another form of funding that can help university researchers to connect with industry is to help the researcher to commercialize technologies developed in university for industry applications. In Malaysia, for example, Govindaraju et al (2009) have found that university researchers firstly need some form of internal support to upgrade their skills in order to become aware of key issues like understanding market requirements and intellectual property implications in order to successfully commercialize university research and technologies.

As mentioned earlier in this section, Government subsidies can help to promote university-industry R&D cooperation in Sri Lanka. Another policy option for this type of subsidy could be to provide funding to help university researchers to commercialize their research with suitable industry partners. However this type of policy initiative is only likely to be fully implemented if the universities have already established formal units dedicated for U-I collaboration, which do exist in a few Sri Lankan universities including the University of Moratuwa, University of Colombo and the University of Kelaniya. Hence the university units are then able to help individual researchers to connect with industrial firms with the support of this type of Government policy measure.

Mode of collaboration

As stated by Sharif and Tang (2014) there is no definite pattern of U-I collaboration. We observed most prominent models of collaboration identified in the literature (D'Este & Patel, 2007) prevailing in Sri Lanka such as training of industry staff at university, research and consultancy contracted to university staff, student placements in industry, and joint conference/seminar events. Still, over 86% of these collaborations emerge as a result of personal contact while only 13% emerge through university initiatives (Table 7). In this regard, Peters and Fusfeld (1982) state U-I collaboration can comprise both formal and informal cooperation. In establishing collaborations using personal contact, as suggested by Lai and Lu (2016), individual personal skills can become an important feature in developing positive collaborative partnerships.

Van Rossum and Cabo (1995) classify U-I collaboration into two types of activities, namely, research and education, which are funded by industrial firms and the government. Our findings supports research collaboration at universities funded by industry under government tax reduction schemes as well as university conducting education programmes for industry.

We observed a few fledgling initiatives where industry sponsored laboratories have been set-up in one university. If other universities in Sri Lanka are to follow this type of initiative there is a need for a “collaboration champion” to drive this type of strategic partnership and this person could be from the university or from the company. Hence, this points to the fact that the focus of U-I collaboration, especially in a developing country context, should be on projects that can be managed, and whose results can be implemented by the collaborating partners given their limited capabilities. If the remit of such projects might be too complex or uncertain, then the risk of failure and loss of trust is very high while the potential of valuable outcomes remains rather low. In addition, as mentioned by Schiller and Lee (2015), individual actors and personalized capabilities are expected to be of particular importance in meaningful U-I collaboration because general institutional trust does not exist among science and industry in many developing countries yet. Also advanced capabilities that help to solidify such linkages are not yet widely spread among actors in science and industry. Hence outstanding individuals (e.g. ‘collaboration champion’), which might be researchers and administrators at universities, entrepreneurs of SMEs, and managers and top engineers in large firms, have to play a more prominent role to help provide the necessary

institutional and financial resources to demonstrate the mutual benefits of U-I collaboration to others.

Barriers for U-I collaboration

“Divergence of objectives” between the university and industry participants has been cited as a problem area with U-I collaboration by universities in Sri Lanka (Table 3 and Table 4). Such divergence could be caused by changes in priorities on the industrial firm side, sometimes driven by changes in management structure or ownership, or on the academic side, driven by cultural factors that may steer the research in a different direction. To help mitigate this problem, the sponsor companies should try to manage the relationship better and more carefully over time.

Barriers for successful U-I collaboration identified by Weerasinghe and Jayawardane (2015) based on a study of SMEs perceptions towards U-I linkages in Sri Lanka also revealed similar findings. That is majority of SMEs suggesting that they do not have an understanding about the university sector and the support which can be obtained from the university sector for promoting innovations within their firms. Hence a key challenge for university-industry networking, as confirmed by Wallin et al (2014), is the difficulty of ‘contextual understanding’ between people from different organizations. Despite some examples of close collaboration between universities and industry, Wallin et al (2014) add that a full insight into a company is difficult, although desirable, for university partners to achieve and vice versa. According to Attygalle et al. (2014) more than 90% of enterprises in Sri Lanka are either small or medium-sized. Studies from Europe and North America on industry perspectives also identifies universities as poor status providers as sources for information on innovation and as collaborative partners in the innovation process (Howells, Ramlogan, & Cheng, 2012). Howells et al. (2012) identified from the UK industry (including SMEs) perspective that major barriers are the lack of knowledge that firms possess around what universities can offer to firms in terms of expertise associated with research and innovation, activities of universities are not relevant to industrial firms, university and industry speak different languages, and collaboration is costly and time consuming. The findings of our study (Table 3 and Table 4) also confirm above findings from the university’s perspective.

One underlying theme of our empirical findings is that there appears to be a disconnect between universities and industry in Sri Lanka, partly because of a lack of knowledge about what universities and firms can offer to each other, especially where

universities and industry might be speaking different languages, as also confirmed by Howells et al. (2012). Hence where the development of U-I linkages are characterized by this type of uncertainty because of a lack of knowledge about what universities and industry can actually offer each other, one option for Government is to create some form of a 'national bridging institution' to facilitate the development of U-I linkages strategically for the benefit of the whole economy. This institution (or higher body) should include representatives from both university and industry in advisory capacities. Also this type of institution could work closely with other areas of Sri Lankan national policy in order to establish if specific sectors might benefit from U-I collaborations. For example, in a sector like agriculture, the scientific and technical requirements of the industry are many and varied. Some parts of this industry might seek innovative approaches to address a national or global issue of concern like health and diet. Here a bridging institute could undertake a wide ranging analysis of local industrial firms and universities to see which organizations might be in a position to address this type of agriculture industry issue and then go about mobilizing key institutional actors by bringing them together via different forums such as conferences and other events.

CONCLUSION

Reflecting on findings from our empirical research undertaken in Sri Lanka, we consider that the technological demand of industrial firms to universities in developing countries is different from that experienced in developed countries, but not essentially weaker or less relevant. Usually the collaborations are not necessarily concerned with technological innovation in a strict sense, but more with adaptation, enhancement, incremental change, and adjustment to local circumstances.

We could also postulate that resource constraints in developing countries do not completely inhibit U-I collaboration. In fact, some academics do actively attempt to overcome various resource barriers. Hence this demonstrates that there are possibilities and potential opportunities open to those academics, with the right level of institutional support and backing, to initiate such linkages.

Furthermore, although in Sri Lanka U-I collaboration is not fully developed, it is however a part of the larger NIS, which needs to be recognized. Accordingly, governments need to earmark funding and other support to public universities in order for the universities to create successful NIS. These issues studied with respect to U-I collaboration in Sri Lanka are neither specific nor distinctive to Sri Lanka. Therefore, findings of our study could

provide valuable insights to university academics/administrators, company managers and policy analysts in other developing countries who may be dealing with similar initiatives to promote university-industry collaboration in their countries.

However, a few limitations in our study need to be acknowledged. Our empirical research findings are based on a single case study approach (i.e. the empirical research evidence was gathered in Sri Lanka, which is seen as the country case study here) in order to explore an under researched area (Yin, 2009). Concurring with other single case study based research outputs like for example, Zott, Amit and Massa (2011), the emergent nature of U-I collaboration in a developing country like Sri Lanka presents the need for exploratory research in this area. Therefore, whilst generalisations cannot be made across other developing country contexts, the findings reported in this paper can be reinterpreted and reconstructed in other developing country contexts. As an exploratory study, we were very selective on the respondents to the survey questionnaire. Therefore, as detailed in the section of *Survey*, 43 key senior academics involved in U-I collaboration across eight universities responded. Although our sample was small, we attempted to perform statistical analysis on the three questions, which were on Likert-type response scales. Results of the factor analysis yielded satisfactory results. Future studies with larger samples could investigate associations between mechanisms for establishing U-I collaboration, barriers in preventing U-I collaboration with industry, and factors motivating academics for U-I collaboration and the level of U-I collaboration. These present opportunities for further research to explore how some of the U-I interactions might already have been initiated in other developing countries and whether these have been evaluated to establish concrete impacts on innovation and entrepreneurship.

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